

The Use of Eye Metrics to Index Cognitive Workload in Video Games

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ABSTRACT

Eye tracking metrics may provide unobtrusive measures of cognitive states such as workload and fatigue and can serve as useful inputs into future human computer interface technologies. To further explore the usefulness of eye tracking for the estimation of cognitive state, the current experiment evaluated saccade, fixation, and pupil-based measures to identify which metrics reliably indexed cognitive workload in a dynamic, unconstrained task (Tetris®). In line with previous studies, our results show that some eye movement features are correlated with changes in workload, manipulated here via task difficulty. Among these were blink duration, saccade velocity, and tonic pupil dilation.

Keywords: Eye Tracking, Cognitive Workload, Saccade, Fixation, Pupil Diameter, Tetris

Index Terms: H.5.2 [User Interfaces] Input devices and strategies

H.1.2 [User/Machine Systems] Human factors

K.8.0 [Personal Computing] Games

1 INTRODUCTION

As technology becomes more complex and pervasive, it is increasingly important to limit the cognitive demands placed upon users. Under this goal, numerous efforts have been designed to measure and reduce an operator's cognitive workload [1]. The present study is a continuation of one such effort [2]. Here, we define workload as the relationship between the processing capacity of the user and the processing requirements of the task [3,4]. Cognitive workload is bounded by the available processing resources of the brain, is coupled with task demands, and fluctuates based on the quantity of concurrent information being processed.

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Eye tracking metrics have been identified as promising unobtrusive indices of cognitive workload. Eye tracking has many benefits, relative to other approaches, in that it provides continuous, objective measurements with high temporal and spatial resolutions and without burdening or interrupting the user.

In this study, we systematically manipulated the difficulty of a Tetris game by increasing the speed at which the block pieces fell. We then used eye tracking to identify which ocular metrics were linearly related to this workload manipulation.

1.1 Background

1.1.1 Negative relationship between blink duration and workload

A blink is the span of time between the onset of a downward eyelid transition until its return to the upward stationary position. In 1996, Morris and Miller concluded blink duration is effected by visual processing demands rather than cognitive workload [5]. Van Orden (2001), however, found contradicting results where blink duration declined as a function of increased workload [6]. In our Tetris task, there were concomitant demands placed on both visual (e.g. block identification) and cognitive (e.g. mental rotation) processes. Therefore, we expect to observe a negative relationship between blink duration and task difficulty.

1.1.2 Negative relationship between fixation duration and workload

Eye fixations, or periods of gaze stability, enable us to discriminate fine details in our surroundings and are influenced by various cognitive processes. Van Orden (2001), examined how fixations correlated with workload during a visuospatial memory task. Specifically, they observed that fixations did not vary as a function of target density [6], which is a potential analogue to general workload. However, this was contradicted by a later study which found that the mean

and maximum duration of fixations increased with workload [7]. Based on these somewhat ambiguous findings, we expect fixation duration to have a small but significant negative relationship with workload.

1.1.3 Positive relationship between saccades and workload

Saccades, large directed eye movements, have a stereotyped velocity profile that is modulated as a function of magnitude. Importantly, peak saccadic velocity measurements are invariant to changes in saccade detection thresholds and therefore provide a more robust index of saccadic activity. Likewise, peak velocity has been shown to be an indicator of cognitive workload [8].

Previously, researchers have used this metric to determine a subjects' attentional engagement with a specific task where a higher peak velocity suggests an increased level of engagement. According to Di Stasi [8] and Galley [9], subjects had a higher level of attentional engagement as the task workload increased. Thus, we expect our results to mirror this phenomenon with saccades exhibiting a positive relationship with workload.

1.1.4 Positive relationship between pupil size and workload

Pupil size, or the measured dilation of the pupils, is responsive to changes in cognitive workload [10]. Specifically, Beatty (1982) reported that the pupils dilated in response to increased mental workload with a peak dilation at about 1-2 seconds after the onset of increased demand. Likewise, other studies have found that once a task is completed or demand reduced, the pupils can constrict either gradually [11, 12] or rapidly [13]. Importantly, this type of pupillary response has been shown to be consistent across both tasks and individuals [14]. Thus, we expect pupil size to have a positive relationship with increased workload.

2 METHODS

Our study included 13 subjects with an age range of 17 to 48 years (mean age of 30.76 years). Sleep history was assessed via survey and ranged from 4 hours to 7.5 hours with a mean of 6.27 hours of sleep the previous night. Video game experience was reported with a range of 0 to 25 hours per week and an average of 4.62 hours per week.

To modulate workload, a version of Tetris was implemented in Psychtoolbox (MATLAB®). Tetris provided a dynamic, unconstrained task while still preserving parametric control of workload [2, 15]. Here, workload was manipulated via tetrad fall speed. Specifically, the rate of vertical travel of the current block piece per unit time. We included fall speeds of 2, 5, and 7 steps per second. In pilot testing, a fall speed of 1 was seen to require little effort, and a fall speed of 8 was reported as too difficult. Every subject was required to complete the task in one session, with self-paced breaks between experimental blocks. Each subject performed two consecutive experimental blocks at each fall speed. Fall speed order was counterbalanced across subjects and was known to the subject before the block started.

Prior to the experiment, subjects performed a 2-minute practice block with a fall speed of 5 to become familiar with the task. While playing Tetris, utilizing the keyboard controls with their right hand, subjects were also asked to perform an auditory oddball task. The oddball task consisted of a series of tones. Most tones were the same low-pitched frequency (background), with an occasional higher frequency tone (target). The subjects were asked to respond to the higher frequency tone via touchscreen with their left hand. This secondary task was designed to assess the current demands of the primary Tetris task via accuracy and reaction time; however, no significant differences in secondary performance were found.

Figure 1: The average fixation heat map of all 13 subjects for fall speed 2.

The trials were conducted in a standard experimental chamber with consistent temperature and lighting. EEG and heart rate were also collected but these data and results are not presented here. The primary

computer ran the Tetris task while a touchscreen monitor, positioned to the left of the primary monitor, ran the auditory discrimination task. The Tobii Pro TX300 eye tracker was used to record eye metrics at 300Hz. The Tobii Pro was positioned below the primary monitor and a nine-point calibration was performed prior to the experiment.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

3.1 Data Analysis

Eye metrics were normalized for each individual by subtracting the mean for that individual, across all conditions (fall speeds). Here, data are represented through normalized bar graphs showing the grand average at each condition. Included are error bars showing the standard error in the estimate of the mean.

3.2 Results

Figure 2: (A) Blink duration. (B) Fixation duration. (C) Saccade peak velocity. (D) Pupil size.

Figure 2A shows blink duration relative to fall speed. The general pattern here shows that the highest blink duration value is at 2 steps per second, then decreases as a function of fall speed. The results aligned with the understanding that longer blinks are perceived to slow response time in fast-paced tasks. Therefore, it was not surprising to observe a tendency to decrease blink duration as the task became more difficult. Although a few subjects did not blink during the experimental blocks, this inter-subject variability was taken into account when the results were normalized. We assessed the effect of fall speed on blink duration with a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) which showed a significant modulation ($F(2,11) = 42.8, p < .001$).

Figure 3: Blink frequency (A) and fixation frequency (B) by fall speed.

To further examine this phenomenon, blink frequency was plotted against fall speed (Figure 3A). Blink frequency was also shown to be highest at the lowest fall speed, and as workload increased, blink frequency decreased. Post-hoc t-tests showed a significant difference between fall speed 2 and fall speeds 5 and 7, although no significant difference between fall speeds 5 and 7. This partially supports the claim that blinks decline as a mechanism to compensate for the increased workload. These results potentially support the hypothesis that blinks have a negative relationship with workload.

Figure 2B depicts fixation duration and its relationship to fall speed, showing that at a fall speed of 2, subjects have the longest average fixation duration. As fall speed increased, fixation duration decreased accordingly. This was confirmed through an ANOVA which showed a strong effect ($F(2,11) = 35.57, p < .001$) on fixation duration. Post-hoc t-tests showed significant differences between all three fall speeds. Figure 3B shows a complementary pattern to Figure 2B. As the task became more difficult, fixations increased in frequency and decreased in duration. Subjects moved their eyes more frequently with shorter fixation durations during periods of high workload.

Figure 2C shows the average saccade peak velocity as a function of fall speed. Overall the trend indicates that at slow fall speeds, saccade peak velocities are reduced, and as fall speed increases so does the peak velocity.

This phenomenon can also be seen in the distribution of saccade amplitudes and velocities (Figure 4). This result aligns with past studies that have shown that as a visuospatial task increases in difficulty, the eyes move more rapidly to process the visual information. A one-way ANOVA again showed a significant result ($F(2,11) = 9.33, p < .001$), and post-hoc t-tests showed a significant difference between fall speed 2 and fall speeds 5 and 7, although no significant difference between fall speeds 5 and 7. This partially supports a positive relationship between saccade peak velocity and workload.

Finally, Figure 2D shows pupil size as a function of fall speed. The graph clearly indicates that a fall speed of 2 is associated with the smallest relative pupil size which then increased with increasing difficulty. This type of tonic pupil dilation has been linked to changes in arousal, which can be engendered with increased workload [15]. The observed modulation in pupil size was significant ($F(2,11) = 65.06, p < .001$), and post-hoc t-tests showed significant differences between all three fall speeds. Comparatively, pupil size showed the strongest relationship with changes in workload within our paradigm. As expected from previous research, pupil size was positively correlated with workload.

3.3 Design Constraints

The study lacked in its ability to control certain factors. Factors include luminance. The lighting in the room was held constant for every subject, but each person is different in their reactions to the light. It is possible that pupil size could have been effected. The experiment also had a small sample size and lacked a control group. This control group would have been a group of subject that would just watch the game play by itself, while the eye tracker monitored eye movement.

3.4 Conclusion

Previous studies have investigated the relationships between eye metrics and cognitive workload and our results supported a number of previous findings. Specifically, blink duration along with fixation duration was observed to have a negative relationship with workload while saccade peak velocity and pupil size exhibited a positive relationship. Importantly, our results show that the strongest ocular indicator of increased workload in this paradigm was tonic pupil size.

Figure 4: Main sequence from one subject. Coloured points represent the centroids of each fall-speed distribution (red = 2, blue = 5, and green = 7).

4 FUTURE WORK

As described above, an important objective of this and related studies is to identify robust indicators of cognitive state. One avenue to future this objective is to compare these ocular results with neural signatures of workload reflected in EEG (collected in our experiment but not reported here). EEG may offer a more nuanced understanding of the neural process that underlie the observed ocular dynamics. In addition, understanding the difference between stress and engagement may enable the future creation of adaptive devices that can infer operator state and throttle task load accordingly.

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